

DHInfra.at: A Shared and Federated Infrastructure for the Austrian Digital Humanities

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Introduction: Research Demands at the Intersection of DH and IT

The motto of DHd 2026, “Not just text, not just data,” succinctly describes the methodological and substantive expansion of the Digital Humanities. Today, humanities research operates with a growing variety of data types, from high-resolution image data and 3D models to audio and video files. In parallel, computational methods such as machine learning and artificial intelligence are becoming standard tools for analysis, including automatic transcription, image recognition, and working with large language models (Vogeler and Hofeneder 2023). This development creates a dire need for powerful, specialized, and easily accessible research infrastructure. Individual institutions are often unable to provide this due to cost and complexity, creating a gap between the methodological needs of DH research and the available resources—capabilities that remain unevenly distributed across disciplines, institutions, and regions (Crane 2022; Trognitz 2021).

The DHInfra.at Project: A National Response

This is where the DHInfra.at project comes in. As a national initiative supported by a consortium of nine Austrian universities and cultural heritage institutions and led by the University of Graz, it establishes a central, federated infrastructure for digital humanities research. The project, funded by the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research (BMBWF) as part of the EU’s Recovery and Resilience Facility, aims to connect fragmented resources and provide researchers with location-independent access to specialized digital infrastructure.

While similar initiatives such as the German NFDI (Hartl, Wössner, and Sure-Vetter 2021) pursue a broader and more richly funded agenda focused on integrated research data management across disciplines, DHInfra.at operates on a smaller scale with a clear focus on providing shared com-

putational resources—particularly GPU infrastructure—rather than comprehensive software ecosystems. This pragmatic scope reflects our current capacities while addressing the most pressing needs identified by consortium partners.

Sustainable integration and governance are ensured through its embedding in the national research infrastructure CLARIAH-AT, which will also coordinate a central helpdesk for user support. Beyond national structures, the GPU infrastructure in Graz is currently designated as a point of interest within a EuroHPC Joint Undertaking network, opening pathways for long-term sustainability through European integration.

Methodology: Five Pillars of a Shared Infrastructure

The methodology of DHInfra.at is based on a cooperative, decentralized approach that bundles expertise and resources. The service and product portfolio, shaped by extensive requirements gathering among consortium partners and their existing project commitments, is divided into five core areas:

1. **Data Capture & Imaging:** Mobile scan robots and multispectral cameras enable high-quality, on-site digitization of cultural heritage objects such as large-format documents or paintings.
2. **Repositories:** A fault-tolerant storage system (Ceph-based) hosts curated, specialized research data repositories with a focus on long-term availability.
3. **Machine Learning:** Dedicated GPU clusters democratize access to high-performance computing. This allows for the training and application of AI models without relying on commercial cloud providers with their data privacy and financial hurdles. Access is facilitated through containerized, reproducible environments and flexible resource allocation to best meet the needs of the DH community (Atzenhofer-Baumgartner 2024).
4. **Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS):** A cluster provides computing power for project-specific applications and specialized databases (e.g., graph databases).
5. **Free and Open Source Software (FOSS):** The coordinated development, evaluation, and provision of open-source software for the DH are promoted and financially supported.

Application Scenarios and Significance

The practical relevance of this infrastructure is demonstrated in concrete application scenarios that bridge the gap from theory to practice. Mobile scanning systems are used to digitize large-format historical documents (TU Wien), the “Middle High German Conceptual Data-

base” (MHDBDB) is being modernized and future-proofed by the IaaS component (University of Salzburg), and projects like DiDip (didip.eu) and many others are already poised to make diverse use of the state-of-the-art GPU infrastructure. DHInfra.at thus not only closes a technical gap but also empowers researchers to explore new methodological paths and tackle complex, data-intensive research questions. The project makes a significant contribution to strengthening the digital humanities in Austria by democratizing access to key technologies and promoting the principles of Open Science and FAIR Data (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

Conclusion and Outlook

The poster will (visually) represent the federated structure of DHInfra.at, its five core service areas, associated projects, and the aforementioned application scenarios. The aim is to illustrate the concrete benefits for DH research in Austria and beyond, and to initiate a dialogue on the challenges and potentials of (national) research infrastructures in the Digital Humanities.

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